

Universiti Brunei Darussalam

BB2208 : Individual Assignment 2 - Case Study Analysis

Hyren Agrotex Global Success Enterprise | Digital HRM Model

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Number of Words : 1582 Words	

Date of Submission : 11 November 2020

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1. Executive Summary

Hyren Agrotex Global Success Enterprise is founded by Harisinshah Haji Tahirudin which was established in 2015. When starting his business, he faced challenges including low capital, difficulty finding the right place of land to proceed with his farming business, shortage of labor & overworking existing labor and lack of adequate infrastructure. In order to become automated and data-driven, digital HRM transformation is the process of modifying organizational HR processes. To ensure a good start, make sure to set a specific target, get everyone on board, always keep it straightforward, prioritize fresh ideas, analyze results, and build the right culture and atmosphere for the health and well-being of all Hyren Agrotex Global Success Enterprise employees within the company.

2. Introduction to Hyren Agrotex Global Success Enterprise

Hyren Agrotex Global Success Enterprise is founded by Harisinshah Haji Tahirudin which was established in 2015. The farm was initially managed on 1 hectare of land which was granted to Harisinshah by the government located in MPK Kampung Bebuloh. Harisinshah main clients are the Department of Agriculture and Agrifood, also other private customers. In January 2019, Hyren Agrotex Global Success Enterprise was one of the eight companies that earned \$140.00 in free loan interest to kickstart their company growth under the LiveWIRE Business Awards Startup Funding Scheme (BASfs) which is highly aimed at fostering entrepreneurship and jobs by providing young companies with seed capital. (Hamit, 2019)

3. Owner of Hyren Agrotex Global Success Enterprise : Harisinshah Haji Tahirudin

Harisinshah Haji Tahirudin started going into paddy farming largely because of this family where he worked part time for his father's farm which was location in Bekiau. After completing his service in the army, Harisinshah Haji Tahirudin decide to pursue agripreneurship as an alternative career after his retirement. Throughout the years, Harisinshah Haji Tahirudin have picked up on how to make use of rise husk, treat seeds and grow healthy rice crops from the courses that he have joined. In his early years, Harisinshah Haji Tahirudin has always been familiarized to how farming could represent an important source of income.

4. **What is Digital HRM Model?**

Digital HR is a process optimization that leverages social, mobile, analytics and cloud (SMAC) technology to make HR more powerful, effective and interconnected. In other words, it's a tectonic change in the way human resources operate. However, the only implementation of emerging technology is not what makes HR digital. As Jeff Mike, from Bersin by Deloitte puts it: "Digital HR should also align culture, talent, structure, and processes to balance efficiency and innovation, as well as to sustain a measurable impact on the greater organization as it continuously transforms."

According to Dave Ulrich, the digital HR journey of any company involves four phases (Author: Neelie Verlinden Neelie Verlinden is the Co-Founder and Editor-in-Chief of AIHR Digital. She's an experienced digital HR & HR Tech writer, Author:, & Neelie Verlinden is the Co-Founder and Editor-in-Chief of AIHR Digital. She's an experienced digital HR & HR Tech writer, 2019) :

4.1. *HR Efficiency*

Companies invest in and develop technology systems that handle HR processes effectively, mostly by established HR technology providers.

4.2. *HR Effectiveness*

Technology is used to enhance activities of people (staffing, training), performance management, communication and function.

4.3. *Information*

Information is shared on the company impact. Data is available, internal data is combined with external data, and people analyzes are used to produce business-relevant insights.

4.4. *Connection / Experience*

Digital HR is used to create a connection between people. Social networks are being leveraged, human experience is being developed, and technology creates a stronger sense of belonging.

5. Factors necessary for successful digitalisation of HRM

The factors that determine the progress of the digitization of HRM practices are still divided into three groups known as the TOP model: technical , organizational and people factors (2016). In terms of technical factors, consideration must be given to application and characteristics, data characteristics and integration.

Organizational variables that assess the performance of HRM digitization can be grouped into two major categories: organizational characteristics and skills and resources. It emerges that the form of HRM scanning approach adopted by companies and its performance are highly influenced by the scale, industry, business area and geographic area in which the company operates. The scale of organisations tends to be positively associated with digitalisation. Indeed, digital transformation is more common in medium and large organizations. The private sector is in a position to make greater use of the benefits gained from the digitalisation of HR activities relative to public sector organisations.

Finally , with regard to human factors, we emphasize in particular: top management support and consumer acceptance. Top management support is one of the most critical factors in assessing the progress of the HRM digitization process. Indeed, HR managers have a crucial role to play in making workers understand the significance of this process, but this can be especially complicated by the challenge of managers themselves in fully understanding digitalisation.

6. Important conditions for successful digitalization of HRM

In order to achieve an effective HRM digitization process, scholars stress that certain requirements must be met.

6.1. Clear identification of objective

First of all, it is important that the goals that this method would accomplish within the organization be clearly and specifically defined. This, in turn, enables the company to recognize the best direction in which to direct its digital activities and enables employees to identify more specifically how these innovations redefine their position in the organization.

6.2. Clear identification of key figure

Second, the recognition of key stakeholders within the company is another key requirement for the digital transformation of HRM. Among these, we should highlight in particular the role played by HR managers. It is important that HR managers believe that they are essential factors for digitization.

6.3. Digital tools as complements to traditional ones

Digital technologies should not be seen as replacements for traditional HR processes, but rather as tools that allow them to be facilitated. However, in order to reach the highest degree of performance and efficiency, certain conventional methods need to be changed to better adapt them to modern technologies.

7. Problem Statement faced by Hyren Agrotex Global Success Enterprise

7.1. Low Capital

The main challenge for Hyren Agrotex Global Success Enterprise was their low capital. He was in need of financial assistance to open up his business and to buy necessary machines and supplies for his farm to operate.

7.2. Inefficient process of preparing and choosing land

Another challenge that was faced by Hyren Agrotex Global Success Enterprise was the quality of soil and its suitability for farming. With no proper examination of the soil granted to him, he could not tell whether the land was suitable for paddy farming; the whole process of preparing and choosing the land has been very inefficient.

7.3. Time consuming

Everything is done by hand; with low capital and not being able to offer machines and supplies, workload becomes double and very time consuming.

7.4. Labour Shortage

When Harisinshah knew that Hyren Agrotex Global Success Enterprise was in short of hands with the double workload, he knew that he needed to hire more farmers, which he was having difficulties with. He ended up hiring Indonesian workers which was not his initial plan which is to hire and open jobs for locals. In addition to that, all the hiring process of a foreign workers are very costly.

7.5. Lack of Proper Farming Infrastructure

Lastly, the lack of proper infrastructure was also part of the struggle that was faced by Harisinshah. Without the right irrigation and drainage systems, in addition to it being overly expensive, it was hard to keep the farm up and running

8. Consequences of Digital HRM Model for Hyren Agrotex Global Success Enterprise

It is clear that digitalization also offers positive and negative consequences on HRM practices, which are :

8.1. Advantages of Digital HRM Model

8.1.1. Cost Saving

As for the benefits, the most widely stressed beneficial feature is cost savings. By incorporating digital technologies, companies can achieve cost savings and they can accelerate processes and knowledge management. By making all computers digitized and reducing the need for jobs, the cost of wages and pensions could be minimized.

8.1.2. Efficiency

The use of HRM digitization may also lead to an increase in performance. In particular, many of the studies studied underscored that the digitization of HRM resulted in time savings, which in the case of HRM; by using machines such as Tractors, they could save time instead of using hand forks. This leads to an improvement in the efficiency of the HRM feature. The HRM method is streamlined, easier and quicker. This allows HR professionals to better focus on activities that are meaningful to their function. The adoption of digitalized HRM practices resulted in a reduction of the work intensity to select candidates, analyze their skills in relation to the requirements required to fill the vacant position and select the subjects to hire. This has translated into a reduction in time and an improvement in the organization's ability to deal with its main objectives.

8.1.3. Effectiveness

As far as productivity is concerned, the research carried out shows that the digitization of HR activities leads to an improvement in administrative quality and HR flexibility and less red tape within the function. The use of digital technologies results in a reduction in the time needed to carry out such tasks.

8.2. Disadvantages of Digital HRM Model

8.2.1.Data Security

Among the drawbacks caused by the digitization of human resource management activities are, in particular, concerns related to data protection and the management of confidential employee information. The need to keep such data confidential can restrict the digitization of HRM practices.

8.2.2.Lack Suitable Skills

Digital skills are important to optimize the potential of digitalisation. However, the research carried out reveals that there is a shortage of appropriate skills. Hyren Agrotex Global Performance Enterprise employees are used to work in the conventional way, having automated machines will lead them to difficulties in running them, which are said to lack the required skills.

8.2.3.Difficulty in using new technologies by employees

New technology would require a new collection of skills, which means that Hyren Agrotex Global Performance Enterprise must send current training staff who will be costly and also keep the technologies up and running and require continuous maintenance.

9. Other successful international companies that applied Digital HRM Model to their business

9.1. Volkswagen

By 2025, German automaker Volkswagen (VW) will spend \$4 billion to improve its digital ecosystem. The massive investment will not only allow Volkswagen to appeal to customers, as the auto industry is undergoing a digital transformation, but will also help the firm take on rivals that are launching comparable strategies. As a result of the investments, five million new Volkswagen brand vehicles will be connected to the Internet of Things every year from 2020. Various mobility technologies will also be introduced to customers with the expectation that they will eventually be incorporated into their everyday lives. For example, a solution that allows car owners to have packages delivered to their car instead of a specific address is currently being created. As well as an integrated billing parking app, and real-time personalized location-based recommendations. The company is also planning a new car-sharing program called "WeShare" which will possibly debut in Berlin in the second half of 2019 with 2,000 electric vehicles. As we have learned from the tweet from Jürgen Stackmann, sales and marketing director of Volkswagen, WeShare is currently undergoing beta testing in the streets of Berlin. With this launch, VW hopes to open up a new market for customers who are not interested in car ownership. VW has reported that it aims to make around \$1.1 billion in sales of new digital services, such as car-sharing, parking and parcel delivery services, by 2025

9.2. IKEA

The Swedish furniture giant is also taking steps to remain important and successful in the future. Through offering creative and highly useful experience for both online and offline customers, IKEA has taken the first steps towards becoming a tech company. The IKEA Place app, an augmented reality platform that enables users to imagine how furniture looks in their own home, was released in 2017. This helps consumers first try out various products and decide what to buy. This app has been downloaded 2 million times and has been widely used. Ikea has also entered the smart home market, offering speakers and smart plugs. The production of such goods, services and strategies would allow IKEA to compete better in the future. Other technology-driven campaigns (such as its virtual reality) and its new sustainability-focused content series have led to its reputation as a digitally creative brand.

9.3. *Domino's Pizza*

Listening to the input and digital welcoming of consumers, Domino was crowned the largest pizza company in the world and eventually handed over to its old rival Pizza Hut. It is also no wonder that four-fifths of Domino's revenues today come from digital platforms. To get where they are today, Domino has changed the company's whole culture, converting it from a fast food business into a company full of programming employees, digital marketers, and other tech staff. The entire organizational structure was also revamped and the focus moved to digital sales and advertisement. It was important that everybody at the top, from the Board of Directors to the CEO, be on board. As a result, Domino's is a "e-commerce company that happens to sell pizza." Thanks to Dom's Pizza bot, consumers can now order from any platform they want (Slack, Facebook Messenger, the Company's mobile app, Twitter using emojis, Google Assistant & Alexa, Smart TVs). These activities help make the user experience more enjoyable and less frictionless. Domino's also took an interest in creating an automatic logistics system for self-driving cars and delivery robots.

9.4. *LEGO*

Through movies, mobile apps and mobile games, LEGO has been able to cater to today's digitally-savvy user groups. An improved digital strategy has helped the company to avoid the verge of bankruptcy and start to prosper. By now, a number of content marketing triumphs have been accomplished that most other brands will kill for and a social approach that places the bulk of its emphasis on community involvement. LEGO's online community allows fans to submit their own ideas for new sets and vote on the recommendations they like the best. If a project receives 10,000 votes, LEGO reviews the design, picks a winner, and creates a new LEGO package that is sold worldwide. This means that LEGO has acknowledged that its customers are the primary source of new concepts and inventions. This strategy has allowed the company to keep launching new product lines that its consumers enjoy and have helped to establish a close relationship with its customers around the world. LEGO has also launched other projects such as LEGO Boost – an app that teaches children to code – and LEGO Life to promote social networking and brand advocacy.

10. Conclusion

In conclusion, digitalization is a fast-moving, scalable, easy-to-use, customer-focused, data-driven, collaborative mechanism that is strategically essential for organizational success. It can be said that digitalization is much more than the mere usage within the organization of digital resources. Rather, it includes applying these instruments to innovate the company model and long-term organizational strategies. Despite there has been a substantial increase in interest in the subject in recent years, there is still no clear description of the causes and effects of the progress of the digital transformation process. This model is subject to certain limitations. It is important to consider all the limitations connected with the method itself.

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